

An Extractive Spectrophotometric Determination of Palladium using Tetrabutylammonium Perchlorate

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An extractive photometric determination of trace amounts of Pd^{II} is described. Pd^{II} forms a reddish brown complex with KI which is extracted into chloroform in the presence of tetrabutylammonium perchlorate. The complex shows an absorption maximum at 448 nm.

There are a number of methods available for spectrophotometric determination of palladium¹. A number of quaternary ammonium salts² have been used with considerable advantage for spectrophotometric determination of metal ions in micro-quantities. We have observed that palladium(II) reacts with potassium iodide to form a reddish brown complex which can be extracted into chloroform in the presence of tetrabutylammonium perchlorate.

Results and Discussion

When a solution of KI is added to an acidic solution of Pd^{II}, it forms a reddish brown anionic complex, PdI₄²⁻. This reacts with tetrabutylammonium cation (Q⁺) to form an ion-pair Q⁺₂(PdI₄)²⁻, which is extracted into chloroform. The complex shows an absorption maximum at 448 nm where the reagent blank does not show any significant absorption.

The optimum pH range for the complex formation is 1.0–7.0. At pH <1 and pH >7, the complex shows inconsistent absorbances. The iodide concentration ranging from 0.01 to 0.15 M and tetrabutylammonium perchlorate concentrations in the range 2 × 10⁻⁴ to 1.5 × 10⁻² M yield constant and maximum absorbance.

Among various organic solvents, viz. carbon tetrachloride, benzene, toluene, ethyl acetate, n-butanol, isoamyl alcohol, methyl isobutyl ketone and chloroform tested for extraction of the complex, chloroform was found to be most effective. A 2 min shaking is sufficient for quantitative extraction with chloroform. The complex remained stable for at least 3 h.

Beer's law is obeyed in the concentration range 5–30 ppm of Pd. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity are 5.02 × 10³ dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 0.021 μg cm⁻² respectively. The standard deviation and coefficient of variation for ten replicate measurements are 0.0006 and 0.12% respectively. The sensitivity of the method is quite high and compares favourably with other well known methods.

The tolerance limits for interference set at the amount required to cause an error not exceeding 2% in the determination of palladium (100 μg) are as follows : Ag^I, Zn^{II},

Cd^{II}, Hg^{II}, Sn^{II}, Pb^{II}, As^{III}, Sb^{III}, Cr^{III}, V^V, Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} (500 μg), and F⁻, Cl⁻, Br⁻, SCN⁻, S₂O₃²⁻, C₂O₄³⁻, PO₄³⁻, citrate, tartrate (1000 μg). However, Cu^{II}, Bi^{III}, W^{VI}, Pt^{IV} and CN⁻ have low tolerance limit. Tolerance limit of Cu^{II} and Bi^{III} can be improved upto 10 times (1000 μg) by EDTA; Fe^{III} and Mo^{VI} upto 7.5 times (750 μg) by KF, and W^{VI} upto 7.5 times (750 μg) by tartaric acid as masking agents.

In the absence of real samples the proposed method was tested for Pd in a number of synthetic mixtures (Table 1).

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS OF SYNTHETIC MIXTURES

Sl. no.	Composition (μg)	Amount of Pd found (μg)
1.	Pd ^{II} (100), Fe ^{II} (500), Mn ^{II} (500), Bi ^{III} (500) ^a	98.05
2.	Pd ^{II} (100), Cr ^{III} (500), Zn ^{II} (500), Cu ^{II} (500) ^a	99.11
3.	Pd ^{II} (100), Co ^{II} (500), Au ^{III} (150), Fe ^{III} (500) ^b	98.93
4.	Pd ^{II} (100), Ni ^{II} (500), Co ^{II} (500), Mo ^{VI} (500) ^b	98.55

^aExtraction done after addition of EDTA.

^bExtraction done after addition of KF.

Experimental

A Hitachi U-3210 spectrophotometer and an Elico-10 pH meter were used. All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Stock solution of Pd was prepared by dissolving palladium chloride (Johnson and Mathey) in distilled water containing a few drops of HCl and standardized³. The working standard solution of known strength was prepared by appropriate dilution. Solutions of 0.05 M tetrabutylammonium perchlorate (Fluka Chemie) was prepared in 95% ethanol and 0.25 M KI (B.D.H.) in distilled water. Buffer solutions of different pH values were prepared by following standard methods⁴. Solutions of diverse ions were prepared in water.

Procedure : An aliquot containing 50–300 μg of Pd^{II} was made to 10 ml with a buffer solution of pH 4.50. To it 2 ml each of KI and tetrabutylammonium perchlorate solu-

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tions were added. The resulting mixture was gently shaken with chloroform (10 ml) for 2 min. The two phases were allowed to separate. The organic extract was separated and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and its absorbance was measured at 448 nm against reagent blank.

To study the interference due to a foreign ion, the respective foreign ion was added to the aqueous solution of Pd^{II} prior to the addition of other reagents.

References

1. J. H. YOE and L. G. OVERHOLSTER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **61**, 2058; L. G. OVERHOLSTER and J. H. YOE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 3224; H. K. DAS and K. G. KAIMAL, *Curr. Sci.*, 1975, **44**, 663.
2. V. ZHENG and W. YU, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1986, **104**, 81046; B. ETIMOVA, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1986, **105**, 218035; K. C. BAYAN and H. K. DAS, *Curr. Sci.*, 1984, **53**, 915; T. K. THOKDAR, P. K. PARIA, and S. K. MAZUMDAR, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1989, **28**, 443; J. H. MENDEZ, A. A. MATEOS, and E. J. M. MATEOS, *Analyst (London)*, 1986, **111**, 217; S. DADFARNIA and M. SHAMSHIPUR, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1991, **64**, 3063; S. DAS and H. K. DAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1997, **74**, 64.
3. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Analysis", 3rd. ed., ELBS, London, 1962.
4. H. T. S. BRITTON, "Hydrogen Ions", Chapman and Hall, London, 1932.